

ROUND TABLE: “THE BEES STRESS”: FUTURE PERSPECTIVES AND CO-WORKING

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Abstract

The BEESNESS project resulted from a dynamic and fruitful transatlantic collaboration that provided a wealth of novel information about Caatinga bees and their ecosystems. The project was recognised in 2020 with the Prize for Scientific Research and Technological Development of the Commemorations of the Vth Centennial of the Magellan Circumnavigation Travel, which honored the whole team and served as an additional motivation to the whole team. Over 115 outputs were produced, from publications, open access datasets, communications, reports, Master dissertations, contribution to PhD theses, organisation of workshops and seminars, training of other early career researchers and graduation students, app development, outreach activities to school students and the public, and mobilities for exchange, knowledge transfer and networking. From the research work developed we highlight in particular: (i) the assessment of bee biodiversity in the Caatinga biome and in the different areas of production of export fruits, i.e. areas under conventional cultivation with application of pesticides, areas under organic cultivation and areas in transition; (ii) the establishment of a quality profile for melipona honey, with application to quality and origin certification, valuing the local producers; (iii) the assessment of sensitivity to pesticides of several melipona species from the Caatinga, of value to the management of pesticides use in the Valley; (iii) the health assessment of the mandaçaia of the Caatinga, contributing relevant information to the establishment of protection and conservation measurements; and (iv) the omics results obtained, from primers to bees barcoding, to metatranscriptomic data on the native bee species or the protein-ligand modelling approach to understand mechanisms of toxicity and predict hazardous effects. The data gathered provided a basis to the continued inventory of these species, their protection and the sustainable management of agricultural production in the São Francisco Valley. Overall, the work brought new insight and questions for future research and collaboration, related solitary bees, Caatinga melipona species, their life cycle, social structure and behaviour, opening perspectives and setting the ground for continued collaboration.

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